

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF POSTNATAL ONTOGENETIC DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS OF YOUNG CHILDREN (1–3 YEARS OLD) IN THE ARAL SEA REGION.

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Relevance. The Aral Sea region is recognized as an ecological disaster zone, where a combination of factors (drinking water contamination with pesticides, high mineralization, and dust and salt storms from the dry seabed) have a prolonged negative impact on public health. The most sensitive indicator of the territory's environmental well-being is the postnatal ontogenesis of young children. It is during the period from 1 to 3 years that the foundation for physical health is laid, and any deviations in physical development can become irreversible.

Purpose of the study. To conduct a comparative statistical analysis of the main anthropometric indicators and rates of physical development of children aged 1 to 3 years living in various regions of the Aral Sea region in order to identify regional characteristics and risks.

Materials and Methods. Study subjects: 450 children aged 12 to 36 months (230 boys, 220 girls). The study group consisted of ecologically disadvantaged districts (Muynak and Kungrad); the control group consisted of relatively favorable districts.

Methods: Anthropometry (height, weight, chest circumference), centile assessment, and calculation of the Quetelet index. Data were processed using the Student's t-test and correlation analysis. Significance was defined at $p < 0.05$.

Results. Statistical analysis revealed a significant trend toward slower physical development in children in the study group compared to regional standards and the control group. Underweight: 18.5% of children aged 1–2 years had grade I and II malnutrition. By age 3, this figure reaches 22% in the Muynak District. Stunted Growth: The average height of 2-year-old boys in the study group was 84.2 ± 0.8 cm, which is 3.5 cm below the age norm. Dwarfism and subnanism were detected in 12% of children. Harmonious Development: Only 42% of children in the Aral Sea region have harmonious physical development. Disharmonious development is observed in 38% due to underweight, and severely disharmonious development is observed in 20%. Correlation with pathologies: A strong correlation ($r = 0.72$) was found between anthropometric

deficiency and the level of iron deficiency anemia (IDA), which was diagnosed in 78% of the children in the sample.

Conclusions. The physical development of children aged 1-3 years in the Aral Sea region is characterized by a high incidence of microsomatic and dysharmonic development. The predominant abnormality is a combination of growth and weight deficits, indicating chronic nutritional deficiency and the adverse effects of toxic environmental factors on the endocrine system. Statistically, environmental stress in the region has been shown to be the primary factor inhibiting postnatal ontogenesis